

Workshop: Active Learning Teaching Methods for Engineering Ethics Education

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Abstract

This workshop, conducted by the lead editor of the forthcoming Routledge International Handbook of Engineering Ethics Education, focuses on exploring active learning teaching methods in engineering ethics education. Beginning with a whole-group discussion to define ethics in engineering education, facilitators will present an overview of trends and teaching methods outlined in the handbook. These methods include case studies, project-based learning (PB), value-sensitive design, service-learning, arts-based methods, and reflective and dialogical approaches. Participants will then engage in hands-on activities, selecting one ethics topic (e.g., environmental sustainability, social justice, equity, diversity, and inclusion) and one active learning pedagogy (case studies and dilemmas, PBL, or reflective approaches) and explore their integration into one of their programs or modules. The workshop aims to familiarize participants with the handbook, promote its utility for educators, and provide a platform for understanding and applying concepts from its chapters. Participants will work collaboratively to identify ethical issues and apply chosen methods to engineering modules, fostering critical discussion, and planning for ethical integration. By the end of the workshop, participants will be able to define ethics in engineering education, recognize various ethical issues, identify active learning methods for teaching ethics, describe plans for integrating ethics into modules, evaluate proposed activities, and understand the content of the forthcoming handbook. This workshop aligns with conference themes on active learning, innovative experiences in engineering education, and ethics and sustainability.

Keywords: Active Learning; Engineering Education; Ethics; Teaching Methods.

1 Introduction

The facilitators of this session are authors of the "International Handbook of Engineering Ethics Education," to be published by Routledge in 2024. The handbook covers six themes – Foundations of engineering ethics education, Interdisciplinary contributions to engineering ethics education, Ethical issues in different engineering disciplines, Teaching methods in engineering ethics education, Assessment of different aspects of engineering ethics education, and Accreditation and engineering ethics education. This workshop focuses on one of these themes: **Teaching methods in engineering ethics education.**

The workshop will start with a whole-group discussion, identifying the meaning of "ethics" in engineering education. Then the facilitators will provide a brief overview of trends and ways forward to support engineering ethics instruction, followed by a brief definition of each of the six teaching methods covered in the book: case studies, project-based learning (PBL), value-sensitive design (VSD) and design-based learning (DBL), service-learning and humanitarian engineering education, arts-based methods, and reflective and dialogical approaches. The facilitator has taught using all the active learning approaches covered, and her overview slides will include images illustrating her own applications.

Most of the workshop time will be spent applying the methods; each participant will select a method they would like to explore from the standpoint of integrating **engineering ethics** into their programs or modules.

The facilitators' motivations for this workshop/hands-on session are to build participants' familiarity with the forthcoming handbook, to promote the handbook as a helpful tool for educators, to give educators a chance

to understand and apply concepts from the various chapters, and to provide a focused time for everyone at the PAEE/ALE conference to focus on ethical issues for an hour.

This workshop relates directly to one of the following conference themes:

- Experiences in Active Learning and PBL in engineering education
- Innovative experiences in engineering education
- Ethics and sustainability in engineering education

2 Activities

Each participant will select one of the six proposed teaching methods and join a group dedicated to exploring that method. Each group will receive a handout about the method to use as a guide. Once the groups are assembled, the facilitators will ask each group to identify an ethical issue they would like to develop together and an engineering module within which they would like to apply. As they work collaboratively, they can define the module broadly (e.g., mathematics, chemistry, thermodynamics, statics and strengths of materials, bridge design, or a dedicated ethics module for engineers).

Learning outcomes are as follows. At the end of this workshop, participants will be able to:

- define what ethics means in the context of engineering education,
- identify/name a range of issues relevant to engineering ethics education,
- identify/name a range of active learning methods used to teach ethics in engineering,
- describe a plan for using one of the recommended teaching methods to integrate a new/additional aspect of ethics into one of the modules they teach,
- critically evaluate and discuss activities proposed by others for integrating ethics using active learning methods, and
- describe the forthcoming handbook and identify/name some of the topics covered in it.

The primary literature supporting this workshop is by Polmear et al. (forthcoming), Herzog et al. (forthcoming), Routhe et al. (forthcoming), Gammon et al. (forthcoming), Daniel et al. (forthcoming), Hitt et al. (forthcoming), Marin et al. (forthcoming). The facilitators will draw from their reading of the pre-prints of these chapters.

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